

A Classification Problem Formulation for the Reliability Assessment of End-To-End Communication among Cyber Devices of Cyber-Physical Systems

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Abstract— Telecommunication Networks (TLCNs) enable the control of Cyber-Physical Systems (CPSs). Reliable End-to-End (E2E) communication among TLCN devices is fundamental to prevent CPS failures. Simulating the complex underlying phenomena that cause E2E communication failure, such as transmission delays and package dropouts, might be computationally expensive, challenging the reliability assessment of E2E communication. To tackle this issue, we reframe the E2E communication as a classification problem to streamline its reliability assessment. We use Gradient Boosting (GB) as an example of an off-the-shelf classifier that can be tailored to the purpose of estimating the E2E communication success or failure, without relying on the long-running simulation of the information processing through the nodes of a TLCN embedded into a CPS. The CPS considered as case study is an Integrated Power and Telecommunication Network (IP&TLCN) system.

Keywords— Cyber-Physical Systems, Telecommunication Network, Power Network, End-to-End Communication, Classification, Gradient Boosting.

I. INTRODUCTION

Telecommunication Networks (TLCNs) are fundamental in the deployment and operation of Cyber-Physical Systems (CPSs) as they enable communication among cyber devices [1], [2]. Reliable End-to-End (E2E) communication is needed to effectively send information packets from an Origin device to a Destination (O-D) device through a transmission channel (e.g., the TLCN) [3], [4]. However, assessing transmission reliability between different O-D pairs in the CPS is challenged by the large computational resources needed to simulate the interaction of the TLCN with the rest of the CPS.

Hierarchical modeling approaches can help address this issue [5]: CPSs can be mapped into layers, e.g., the physical devices layer and the cyber devices layer, in which the devices are independently characterized by their own model, untangling the interdependencies among devices. A master co-simulation

procedure coordinates the interaction among the diverse models, enabling the simulation of the entire system by coupling the twinned responses between cyber and physical components. Still, TLCN reliability assessment may turn impractical due to the large number of possible scenarios that are to be considered under a combinatorial number of failure modes, e.g., delay and dropout of TLCN nodes and links, and expensive underlying procedures, e.g., routing protocols.

We propose an alternative E2E communication reliability assessment by formulating the E2E communication success as a classification problem: for each O-D pair, we train a binary classifier on a set of artificially generated simulations of a high-fidelity CPS model, in which a TLCN interacts with a variety of devices.

We exemplify the approach using a Gradient Boosting (GB) classifier [6] due to its proven effectiveness in learning complex behaviors and ease of tuning. As a case study, we consider a CPS consisting of an Integrated Power and Telecommunication Network (IP&TLCN) [7] system that relies on a TLCN to transmit distributed electrical measurements and control inputs in a power grid. The training dataset comes from operational scenarios simulated with a long-running physical model developed in [8]. Without loss of generality, we show the application of the classification-based approach for a single O-D pair: five alternative GB classifiers with different hyperparameters are trained and their performance quantified using the Area Under the Curve of the Receiver Operating Characteristic (AUC-ROC) score, suggesting that this is a viable approach to assess the E2E communication success. Finally, we compute the reliability curve for the same O-D pair using the traditional simulation-based approach and the herein proposed classification-based alternative, obtaining a small Root Mean Squared Error (RMSE) and significant savings of computational time.

The remainder of the paper is organized as follows. Section 2 describes the distributed E2E communication models. Section 3 briefly describes the GB approach. Section 4 presents the case study. Finally, Section 5 concludes the work.

II. PROBLEM SETTING

A TLCN is represented as an undirected graph $G = (V, E)$, whose vertices $V = \{1, 2, \dots, n_V\}$ are the TLCN nodes and edges $E = \{e_s | e_s \in V \times V, s = 1, 2, \dots, n_E\}$ are the TLCN links. In a discrete-time setting, to each instant $k = 0, 1, 2, \dots$, corresponds a time $t_k \geq 0$, at which each edge $e_s \in E$ is assigned a time delay $t_d(e_s, t_k) > 0$ (e.g., modeled as a reflected Weiner process [7]), so that vector $\vec{t}_d(t_k)$ captures the time delays across all TLCN links:

$$\vec{t}_d(t_k) = \left(t_d(e_1, t_k), t_d(e_2, t_k), \dots, t_d(e_{n_E}, t_k) \right)^T \quad (1)$$

The TLCN structure might change in time due to random disconnections of nodes or links (e.g., modeled by disconnection probabilities p_d^v and p_d^e , respectively [7]). We track at each time t_k the status of each node $v \in V$ as $\pi_{\text{node}}^{(v)}(t_k) \in \{0, 1\}$, and of each link $e_s \in E$ as $\pi_{\text{link}}^{(s)}(t_k) \in \{0, 1\}$, where 1 means available and 0 non-available:

$$\vec{\pi}_{\text{node}}(t_k) = \left(\pi_{\text{node}}^{(1)}(t_k), \pi_{\text{node}}^{(2)}(t_k), \dots, \pi_{\text{node}}^{(n_V)}(t_k) \right)^T \quad (2)$$

$$\vec{\pi}_{\text{link}}(t_k) = \left(\pi_{\text{link}}^{(1)}(t_k), \pi_{\text{link}}^{(2)}(t_k), \dots, \pi_{\text{link}}^{(n_E)}(t_k) \right)^T \quad (3)$$

The TLCN state vector $\vec{x}(t_k) \in \mathcal{X} \subset \mathbb{R}^{n_x}$, $n_x = n_V + 2n_E$, represents at each time t the TLCN time delays, and nodes and links states. By denoting the j -th state variable as $x^{(j)}(t_k)$, then:

$$\vec{x}(t_k) = \begin{pmatrix} \vec{t}_d(t_k) \\ \vec{\pi}_{\text{node}}(t_k) \\ \vec{\pi}_{\text{link}}(t_k) \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} x^{(1)}(t_k) \\ x^{(2)}(t_k) \\ \vdots \\ x^{(n_x)}(t_k) \end{pmatrix} \quad (4)$$

The set of all O-D pairs in the TLCN is denoted $\Omega = \{\theta_i | \theta_i = (o_i, d_i) \in V \times V, i = 1, 2, \dots, n_\Omega\}$. A transmission function $\phi: \Omega \times \mathcal{X} \rightarrow \{0, 1\}$ determines the communication outcome for any O-D pair $\theta_i \in \Omega$ based on the TLCN condition $\vec{x}(t_k)$, where $\phi(\theta_i, \vec{x}(t_k))$ returns 1 if the transmission between o_i and d_i is successful, or 0 if it fails. Figure 1 sketches this for a generic TLCN along a generic l -th scenario of $\eta_l + 1$ instants. Typically, ϕ is modelled as a memoryless process (i.e., its output at any time t_k depends only on the TLCN conditions at time t_k , $\vec{x}(t_k)$, and not on previous ones), and involves, for a generic l -th scenario:

1. simulating the TLCN dynamics in terms of the evolution of $\vec{x}(t_k)$;
2. simulating routing protocols (e.g., Open Shortest Path First (OSPF) [9]) by solving a shortest path problem (e.g., via Dijkstra algorithm [10]) to find a path of TLCN nodes $\mathcal{P}_{\theta_i} = (v_1, v_2, \dots, v_n)$, $v_1 = o_i$, $v_n = d_i$, with a total time delay $T_d(\mathcal{P}_{\theta_i}, t_k)$, where:

$$T_d(\mathcal{P}_{\theta_i}, t_k) = \begin{cases} \sum_{k=1}^{n-1} t_d((v_k, v_{k+1}), t_k) & \text{if path exists} \\ +\infty & \text{if no path exists;} \end{cases} \quad (5)$$

Fig. 1. discrete time evolution of TLCN state variables and the E2E communication outcomes

Fig. 2. The elements that are used to compute the reliability of an O-D pair

3. checking the transmission success if $T_d(\mathcal{P}_{\theta_i}, t_k) \leq t_{\theta_i}^{\max}$, for some maximum latency $t_{\theta_i}^{\max} > 0$.

For N scenarios in which the E2E communication is successful up to τ_{miss} or fails at least once before τ_{miss} , we can estimate the E2E communication reliability for a specific O-D pair $\theta_i \in \Omega$ over a mission time τ_{miss} : at each generic k -th time step, a binary indicator $C_{l,k}$, $l = 1, 2, \dots, N$, is assigned the value 0 if the E2E communication is successful up to time t_k , or 1 otherwise, as exemplified in Figure 2. Thus, the reliability $r(t_k)$ at the k -th time step is:

$$r(t_k) = 1 - \frac{1}{N} \sum_{l=1}^N C_{l,k} \quad (6)$$

It is worth pointing out that this E2E communication reliability assessment procedure entails computing the shortest paths involving many O-D pairs, that for real-sized TLCNs soon becomes impractical due to the large dimensions of V , E and the long-running times of the first-principle models used to emulate

the underlying TLCN phenomena; this in practice challenges the E2E communication reliability assessment for each O-D.

To address this, we propose bypassing the simulation-based step by, instead, learning the E2E communication outcomes via binary classification: for each O-D pair $\theta_i \in \Omega$, a classifier $\hat{\phi}_i(\vec{x}(t_k))$ learns the binary E2E communication outcomes based solely on the TLCN condition $\vec{x}(t_k)$, i.e., a mapping $\hat{\phi}_i: \mathcal{X} \rightarrow \{0,1\}$ that acts as a surrogate of $\phi(\theta_i, \vec{x}(t_k))$. Then, the outcomes of the trained classifiers are used for the estimation of the E2E communication reliability of Eq. (6).

III. GRADIENT BOOSTING FOR E2E COMMUNICATION RELIABILITY ASSESSMENT

Gradient Boosting (GB) [11], [12] is a learning technique for regression and classification, popular due to its capacity to learn complex relationships while maintaining relatively simple tuning. In a nutshell, GB combines sequentially several weak predictors (typically decision trees [12]) that learn from the residual errors of the previous ones, resulting in a strong predictor. Fine tuning a GB model involves adjusting, among others, the number of weak estimators M and the maximum depth of the regression trees d_{\max} , and choosing an appropriate loss function (typically the Area Under the Curve of the Receiver Operating Characteristic (AUC-ROC) score [13], for binary classification).

In this work, we use GB to learn the E2E transmission outcomes $\phi(\theta_i, \vec{x}(t_k))$ between O-D pairs $\theta_i \in \Omega$. For this, a dataset $\{\mathbf{X}_l, \mathbf{Y}_l\}_{l=1:N}$ of N scenarios is built: for any l -th scenario, the k -th row of matrix \mathbf{X}_l corresponds to time t_k , and stores the values of the TLCN state vector $\vec{x}_l^T(t_k)$, whereas the j -th column of \mathbf{X}_l are the values of the j -th state variable $x_l^{(j)}(t_k)$. Denoting $\eta_l + 1$ the rows number, which might vary across scenarios due to different scenario durations, then:

$$\mathbf{X}_l = \begin{bmatrix} \vec{x}_l^T(t_0) \\ \vec{x}_l^T(t_1) \\ \vdots \\ \vec{x}_l^T(t_{\eta_l}) \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} x_l^{(1)}(t_0) & x_l^{(2)}(t_0) & \dots & x_l^{(n_x)}(t_0) \\ x_l^{(1)}(t_1) & x_l^{(2)}(t_1) & \dots & x_l^{(n_x)}(t_1) \\ \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ x_l^{(1)}(t_{\eta_l}) & x_l^{(2)}(t_{\eta_l}) & \dots & x_l^{(n_x)}(t_{\eta_l}) \end{bmatrix}_{(\eta_l+1) \times n_x} \quad (7)$$

The i -th column of matrix \mathbf{Y}_l stores the E2E transmission outcomes for the corresponding O-D pair $\theta_i \in \Omega$:

$$\mathbf{Y}_l = \begin{bmatrix} \phi(\theta_1, \vec{x}_l(t_0)) & \phi(\theta_2, \vec{x}_l(t_0)) & \dots & \phi(\theta_{n_\Omega}, \vec{x}_l(t_0)) \\ \phi(\theta_1, \vec{x}_l(t_1)) & \phi(\theta_2, \vec{x}_l(t_1)) & \dots & \phi(\theta_{n_\Omega}, \vec{x}_l(t_1)) \\ \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ \phi(\theta_1, \vec{x}_l(t_{\eta_l})) & \phi(\theta_2, \vec{x}_l(t_{\eta_l})) & \dots & \phi(\theta_{n_\Omega}, \vec{x}_l(t_{\eta_l})) \end{bmatrix}_{(\eta_l+1) \times n_\Omega} \quad (8)$$

Since ϕ is memoryless, we can stack the data to construct an input matrix (\mathbf{X}), output matrix (\mathbf{Y}) and drop the time indexing; this property also allows us to randomly split into training and validation datasets, putting aside the time dependence. By denoting $n_N = \eta_1 + \eta_2 + \dots + \eta_N + N$, then:

$$\mathbf{X} = \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{X}_1 \\ \mathbf{X}_2 \\ \vdots \\ \mathbf{X}_N \end{bmatrix}_{n_N \times n_x}, \quad \mathbf{Y} = \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{Y}_1 \\ \mathbf{Y}_2 \\ \vdots \\ \mathbf{Y}_N \end{bmatrix}_{n_N \times n_\Omega} \quad (9)$$

As a result, we can obtain a mapping $\hat{\phi}_i: \mathcal{X} \rightarrow \{0,1\}$ that predicts the E2E transmission outcomes for O-D pair θ_i by training a GB classifier according to $\mathbf{X} \rightarrow \mathbf{Y}[:, i]$. In this case, each k -th row in \mathbf{X} is an input to the classifier, whose output should, ideally, be equal to the corresponding E2E transmission outcome, i.e., $\mathbf{Y}[k, i]$.

Finally, as said, we use $\hat{\phi}_i(\vec{x}(t_k))$ to estimate the E2E communication reliability for the pair θ_i following the exact same procedure detailed in Section II, via Eq. (6).

IV. CASE STUDY

We consider an Integrated Power and Telecommunication Network (IP&TLCN) [8] system, whose flowchart is sketched in Figure 3. At each time t_k , Smart Monitoring Devices (SMDs) send power network monitoring data $\vec{u}^\dagger(t_k)$ to the Control Center (CC) (bottom-up). In turn, the CC sends control actions $\vec{u}^\dagger(t_k)$ to devices in the power network (top-down). $\Psi(u, t_k)$ is the transmitted data u at time t_k considering the successful/failed E2E communication between O-D pairs in the TLCN with the topology in Figure 4 and $n_x = 25$ state variables. Without loss of generality, we focus on the bottom-up flow: SMDs are located at TLCN nodes 1 to 6, whereas the CC is at node 7, resulting in the $n_\Omega = 6$ O-D pairs $\Omega = \{(1,7), (2,7), (3,7), (4,7), (5,7), (6,7)\}$.

The training data is generated using [8], which yields a total of $N = 3,607$ scenarios, where each l -th scenario has a count of data points ranging from $\eta_l = 3$ to $\eta_l = 384$, resulting in time durations from 0.75 to 96 hours. Stacking the scenarios results in a total of $n_N = 736,456$ observations of E2E transmission

Fig. 3. Hierarchical scheme of the IP&TLCN

Fig. 4. TLCN topology

TABLE II. NUMBER OF TRANSMISSION FAILURES FOR EACH O-D PAIR OBSERVED IN THE DATASET

O-D pair	(1,7)	(2,7)	(3,7)	(4,7)	(5,7)	(6,7)
Count	0	4	2	0	0	302

outcomes for all O-D pairs (i.e., rows in \mathbf{X} and \mathbf{Y}), with the observed number of failures shown in Table I. From now on, without loss of generality, we focus on O-D pair $\theta_6 = (6,7)$ by training classifier $\hat{\phi}_6$, as this is the pair that exhibits the highest number of E2E transmission failures.

After processing the available data, the considered \mathbf{X} and \mathbf{Y} for θ_6 are composed by 31,888 rows, which we split into training (80%) and test (20%). We benchmark five alternative GB models, each characterized by different values of the number of regression trees M and their maximum depth d_{\max} ; for GBC_1-4, we manually set these hyper-parameters, whereas, for GBC_5, we run a grid search considering $M \in \{10,15,20, \dots, 100\}$ and $d_{\max} \in \{1,3,5,7,9\}$. Table II summarizes the classification results, where the fined tuned model GBC_5 achieves the highest AUC-ROC scores in both training and test. In Figure 5, the confusion matrices for all the alternative GB models are plotted, where we notice that GLC_5 better predicts successful E2E communication outcomes than failures (i.e., the rate of incorrect predictions for label “0” is higher than that for label “1”). This is expected due to the imbalance in the dataset, where the number of unsuccessful E2E communication (label 0) is extremely rare. Regarding time execution, while the simulation-based approach described in Section II and applied to this case study takes roughly 3.5 minutes to compute all the E2E communication outcomes, the novel classification-based approach needs only 207.88 milliseconds (around 1,000 times faster).

TABLE I. AUC-ROC SCORE FOR EACH CLASSIFIER TRAINED ON THE E2E COMMUNICATION SUCCESS OF O-D PAIR (6,7)

Model	Hyper-parameters		AUC-ROC score	
	M	d_{\max}	Training (%)	Test (%)
GBC_1	5	3	77.41	74.07
GBC_2	10	3	86.89	83.33
GBC_3	5	8	86.89	84.25
GBC_4	10	8	90.32	83.33
GBC_5	80	5	100.00	88.88

Fig. 6. Training and test confusion matrices for GB classification, O-D pair (6,7)

Fig. 5. Comparison of the reliability curves for O-D pair $\theta_6 = (6,7)$ obtained with the original data and the predicted data from the classifier

Figure 6 shows the reliability curves obtained with the simulation-based data and the classification-based approach that uses GBC_5, following Eq. (6). For a mission time $\tau_{miss} = 48$ hours, the maximum error between the curves amounts to $1.09\text{e-}03$, whereas their Root Mean Squared Error (RMSE) is $3.36\text{e-}04$, showing that the classification-based approach is well-suited for assessing TLCN reliability with high precision and low computational burden. The small reliability overestimation obtained with the classification-based approach is due to mispredictions of label “0,” which occur with higher rates and causes the unreliability indicator to output 1 instead of 0.

V. CONCLUSIONS

This paper presents a data-driven approach to learn the distributed End-to-End (E2E) communication outcomes between Telecommunication Network (TLCN) devices. Instead of simulating the complex and time-consuming underlying phenomena of TLCNs, we reframe the problem as a classification task: a binary classifier discerns whether the E2E transmission between an Origin-Destination (O-D) pair succeeds or fails solely based on the TLCN conditions. For the classification, we resort to Gradient Boosting (GB) as an off-the-shelf classifier method due to its proven capabilities to learn complex tasks. Our case study involves a TLCN embedded in a CPS, in which we show that tuning the GB model improves the classification performance, achieving an AUC-ROC score of nearly 89% on the test dataset. We demonstrate the practical use of the classification-based approach by computing the reliability curve for an O-D pair, observing a small RMSE, highlighting the model precision. Finally, the proposed solution can streamline the reliability computation by accelerating simulations, reducing the need for extensive TLCN models.

Future work will involve addressing the issue of imbalanced dataset for the construction of the classifiers by resorting to adequate techniques for such purpose and evaluating the impact of classifier error for the reliability estimation by taking into account existing uncertainties.

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